

ISic0637

I.Sicily inscription 0637

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble (?)

Object

ash chest

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

'periferia di Siracusa'

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Avola, private collection

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Π(ούβλιε) · Κλώδιε

2. Κορνηλιανέ

3. εὔσεβῆ · χαέρεχαῖρε

Apparatus

Text of Manganaro 1994

Translation (en)

Publius Claudius Cornelianus, a pious man, farewell.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644879

PHI 332968

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1994.0760

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 44.0791

Manganaro, G. 1994. Iscrizioni, epigrafi ed epigrammi in Greco della Sicilia orientale di epoca romana. *Mélanges de l'École Française de Rome: Antiquité.* 106: 79-118. At 83-84 no.1 fig.3

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